

CHARACTERISTICS OF POLITICAL DISCOURSE AND TRANSLATION OF IT.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433754>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 02-October 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 06- October 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 12- October 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

*Discourse, proposition, evaluative
and aggressive political discourse,
political dialect, exorcism, agitated
enthusiasm,*

ABSTRACT

*These days, a wide range of academic disciplines,
including political science, linguistics, philosophy,
psychology, cultural studies, and many more, frequently
use the concept of discourse. This idea is said to have
evolved into a certain paradigm. As a result, depending
on the academic subject, different definitions of this
concept exist.*

Introduction. These days the idea of talk is broadly utilized in an assortment of scholarly areas counting political science, phonetics, reasoning, brain research, social thinks about and numerous other. This idea is credited to ended up a certain worldview as well. In this way, there's an assortment of approaches to characterize this idea depending on a certain scholastic field. The paper points to supply a diagram of talk as an idea and talk about its unconventional characteristics from the point of see of etymology. When giving the definition of talk, N. D. Arutyunova gives three viewpoints to talk about. The primary one would be when talk is respected a coherent content along with a set of extralinguistic angles counting practical, sociocultural, mental ones and other. Talk can too be seen as a content inside a particular setting. The final would be when talk is respected as discourse seen as aiming social activity, a component of human interaction and cognition. It is beneficial specifying that N. D. Arutyunova sees talk as discourse imbedded in setting. As E. S. Kubryakova focuses out, from the point of see of cognitive etymology the qualification between the two ideas (content and talk) is very normal since it relates with the differentiate between cognition and its result. Agreeing to E. S. Kubryakova, talk can be accepted as a cognitive handle related to discourse generation whereas a content is the result of discourse. In this way, analysts recognize talk and content agreeing to a number of criteria, such as usefulness and structure, flow and statics, prepare and result, topicality and virtuality. In Russian etymology, V. Z. Demyankov given the foremost comprehensive definition of this idea. V. Z. Demyankov claimed that talk is 'an arbitral portion of content comprising of more than one sentence or an autonomous portion of sentence; which is as a rule wrapped around some basic concept, makes the in general setting, portraying individuals, objects, circumstances, time, activities and etc.' According to this definition, the beginning structure of discourse may be a grouping of straightforward suggestions associated by conjunction, disjunction, etc. Hence, we are able

propose that talk may be a wide idea counting two unequal components, i.e. content and discourse. At the same time, talk may be a cognitive handle, and content is its result. On the entire, talk may be a complex communicative marvel inside the setting of extralinguistic angles, which isn't rise to content. A number of researchers have been considering political talk over the final few a long time since this wonder is respected as the type of talk which influences society to a greater degree. Agreeing to A. N. Baranov, political talk incorporates all discourse acts of political talks and the rules of open legislative issues, having particular traditions. The significance of political talk lies within the truth that well-maintained political communication gives for coming to agreement within the society. This infers that a lawmaker ought to aim making choices from which the society would advantage enormously. The most point of political talk is to create the beneficiaries accept in the need of politically redress activities or assessments. So, it isn't to portray but to induce, so that the beneficiary would have a few eagerly, convictions and require for certain activities. When it comes to discussing the adequacy of political talk, the analysts would examine it in accordance with the most point of political talk. It is self-evident that talking almost the viability of political talk it is inconceivable to dodge one of the foremost vital components of political discourse, i.e. persuasiveness. As Rathmayr put it, lawmakers in their discourse work with certain symbols, it is effective depending on the degree to which these images correlate with public consciousness. A lawmaker ought to be able of finding perfect way">the most perfect way to address his group of onlookers taking into thought their conclusions, convictions and so on. In agreement with E. V. Budaev and A. P. Chudinov, we propose that there are a few sources through which we are able comprehend political talk and dialect. The most source of political dialect that the gathering of people touches upon is mass media, counting daily papers, radio, tv and the Web. There's moreover a source of political regulation talk comprising flyers, parliamentary talks about, open discourse, distributed records, etc. Political talk is considered particular since it has a number of impossible to miss highlights or characteristics. In their discourse, lawmakers utilize specific terms and ideas, which implies that their vocabulary is professional, at the same time common words and expressions when utilized in political setting might have a distinctive meaning contradicted to their normal one. The structure of political talk is additionally particular, because it is comprised of specific discourse procedures normal of political talk. The researchers also note that talk has an extraordinary talked and composed frame, i.e. pauses and pitch. They say that politician's discourse contains twice as many important stops as other people's, and these stops tend to be longer which makes it possible to compare this sort of discourse with dramatic exhibitions [7, p. 46]. Because it was said in the presentation to this paper, discourse as a entirety and political talk in specific is subject to multidisciplinary investigate and there's a assortment of approaches towards it. In this paper, we recommend that there are at slightest three viewpoints worth talking about. To begin with, political talk can be seen from the point of see of physiology as any other content, in any case, in this case an scholastic would moreover respect the setting and ideologies. Another critical approach to political talk is that of sociopsychology, when analysts endeavor assessing the viability of talk and the degree to which speakers reach their points. And the last viewpoint is one concerning the analysis of individual bases or eagerly and/or the addressee's as well inside certain setting

Discussion. Discourse consists of propositions or fragments of propositions, and the

discourse's substance is frequently, but not always, centered on a concept that serves as its "support," also known as the "subject of discourse" or "discourse topic." Propositions are the logical components of individual proposals, which are parts of discourse; they are connected by logical connections such as conjunction, disjunction, if-then, etc.). Interpreting dialogue, the interpreter constructs fundamental claims based on shared values, setting the fresh data found in another interpreted claim within the framework of the previously received interim or preliminary interpretation, that is:

- develops a number of connections within the text, including anatomic, semantic (types of synonymy and antonymy), referential (references names and descriptions to objects of the real or mental world), and functional viewpoint (the theme of the utterance and what it discusses), among others.

Let's have a look at the following instance from Barack Obama's victory address:

"...If there is anyone out there who still doubts that America is a place where all things are possible; who still wonders if the dream of our founders is alive in our time; who still questions the power of our democracy, tonight is your answer..."¹

- offers fresh facts to the discussion's subject. Let's look at another instance from Barack Obama's address that relates to the recent information:

"...A little bit earlier this evening, I received an extraordinarily gracious call from Senator McCain. Senator McCain fought long and hard in this campaign, and he's fought even longer and harder for the country that he loves. He has endured sacrifices for America that most of us cannot begin to imagine. We are better off for the service rendered by this brave and selfless leader. I congratulate him; I congratulate Governor Palin for all that they've achieved, and I look forward to working with them to renew this nation's promise in the months ahead. ..." ²

Following that, we'll try to demonstrate why it's insufficient to describe political speech solely in language terms, without reference to literary devices. Political discourse is examined within a broader theoretical framework of philology. When attempting to define the effectiveness and intelligence of the political discourse, it is very obvious.

1. Evaluative and aggressive political discourse. So, when trying to characterize the features of the "totalitarian" discourse, it inevitably enters into the description of ethical terms, for example:³

- "speaking in tongues": dominates in declamatory style proclamation, advocacy triumphalism
- idealization of everything mentioned, excessive use of the terminology, and damaging to logic
- exaggerated abstraction and scientology,
- increased criticism and "flame",
- slogans, addiction, exorcism,
- agitated enthusiasm,

¹ American Rhetoric: Barack Obama - President-Elect Victory Speech.

² Charteris-Black, J. Politics and rhetoric: The persuasive power of metaphor. New York., 2011.- P.110.

³ Teun A. van Dijk. Discourse and Context a Sociocognitive Approach. — New York: Cambridge University Press, 2008. — 267 c.

These properties show the insight that have characterized the political discourse and distinguishes it from other types of speech. This insight has implications for, for example, the choice of words.⁴ This illustrates how military action from the battlefield is transferred to a theater play. According to some social psychologists, this sublimation of aggression is ingrained in human nature. Political rhetoric therefore has an aggressive theatrical quality. The insight to the suggestion of a negative attitude is directed at the speaker's political opponents, to the imposition of alternative values and assessments as the most natural and uncontroversial. Because of this, the terms are viewed adversely by opponents and, in some cases, even as an outright insult.

This also explains the peculiarity of "political diglossia"⁵ a totalitarian society where there seems to be two different languages – the language of official propaganda and the usual language. The terms of one language are used in another only with polar opposite rating or are expelled from usage at all. The following groups of statements are used in political discourse⁶:

- ascertaining and regulating act,
- hiding statements supplied in the form of questions,
- interpretations and descriptions of the problems,
- formulating ideas, the author seemingly innovates
- requesting and demands to the authorities, – calling to contribute to any decision and offer of assistance, etc.

Public purpose of political discourse is to inspire people, the citizens of the community, the need for a "politically correct" actions and assessments. In other words, the purpose of political discourse is not to describe, and to convince, awakening in the destination of intentions, to give ground for the belief and inspire action. Therefore, the effectiveness of political discourse can be defined relative to this goal. Speech policy, with a few exceptions, uses the symbols and its success are determined by how these characters are consonant with the mass consciousness: a politician must be able to touch the right chord in the consciousness; policy statements must be placed in the "universe" of opinions and evaluations that is, all the many inner worlds, its addressees, "consumers" of political discourse. Politicians are eager to employ language techniques during speeches, debates, and press conferences in order to appear persuasive. Politicians use rhetorical elements of discourse to captivate the audience during speeches and persuade them of whatever is being delivered.

The interpretation of political dialect comes out into an extraordinary field of think about due to its particular highlights of composed and verbal discourse on political themes, which is indicated by its basic character and the information of this science. Some of the time these highlights are so differing that in arrange to get it them one ought to have an extraordinary information without which it would be exceptionally difficult to clearly see the internal sense on legislative issues or an interpreted piece.

Political writing like all other logical kind of writing have dialects things characteristic to them, that requires the interpreter to be exact and sharp. Most books on common legislative issues are characterized by the enthusiasm of expression, questioning fashion and

⁴ Lakoff G., Johnson M. *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago, 1980.

⁵ Skrebnev Y.M. *Fundamentals of English stylistics*. M.: V. Sh., 1994, 235 p.

⁶ Watts D. *Political Communication Today*. Manchester; New York, 1997.

the particular include is in mixing the components of logical discourse from one side with diverse sincerely colored implies of expression from another side. The interpretation of political writing can be considered in two ways: as a field of etymological movement and as a partitioned field in science.

As a field of phonetic action interpretation of political writing speaks to one of the sorts of uncommon interpretations having as objects of its movement distinctive materials of political character. Subsequently, the ponder of particular highlights of composed and verbal discourse procures extraordinary significance to interpreters (translators). To the highlights specify over have a place the taking after:

- maximal filling the political writing with uncommon political terms, and in verbal discourse (among the lawmakers) – filling it with words of political language – slang.
- nearness of uncommon colloquial expressions and phraseological units in verbal and composed discourse that are seldom utilized in colloquial discourse and common writing.
- the nearness of a few elaborate avoidance from common scholarly standards is now and then exceptionally awesome.
- wide utilization of elliptic developments, particularly in intermittently distributing materials, purposeful publicity and other sorts of politically imperative printing media.
- exactness and excellence of self-expression which is accomplished by the utilization of elliptic developments in conjunction with wide utilization of detached developments.
- the nearness of official composing fashion, for the most part in records of official arrangements that cover regulatory and political questions.
- entirely controlled utilize of verbal shapes and word expressions in uncommon chapters of political writing and political reports.

The purposes of interpretation are so differing, the writings so diverse, and the receptors so changed that one can promptly get it how and why numerous particular definitions of standards and hones of interpretation have been proposed. It's broadly known that interpreters ought to know both the source and the receptor dialects, ought to be commonplace with the subject matter, and ought to have a few office of expression within the receptor dialect. Past these essential necessities there's small understanding on what constitutes true blue deciphering and how the science of phonetics, or indeed the information of dialect structures, can and ought to be connected. For better understanding of the causes of this need of understanding and in arrange to build a framework for the investigation and assessment of the different speculations of interpretation, it is basic to audit the relations between the source, the message, and the receptors within the communication prepare, and too the work of the medium of communication which is utilized.

What does it cruel to act politically? On the confront it, the state would include activities impacting relations between individuals, especially the loyalties and organizations together that shape control and coordinate its streams. The political pronoun is certainly "we", differently comprehensive or elite. To act politically, within the intercultural field, may in this way cruel siding with one culture or the other, or with one viewpoint of a culture against another, to a few degree or another, for one reason or another.

Since interpretation is an activity including dialect, there's a sense in which any and all speculations of interpretation are etymological. There are, be that as it may, three very

distinctive ways in which the standards and strategies of interpretation have been defined and protected. These assorted approaches to the issues of interpreting are basically things of distinctive points of view or foci. In case the center of consideration is on specific writings (and particularly in case these are of a so-called scholarly quality), the basic hypothesis of interpretation is for the most part best respected as philological. In the event that, be that as it may, the center of consideration is on the correspondences in dialect frame and substance, that's , on the basic contrasts between the source and receptor dialects, the comparing hypothesis may be respected as phonetic. At long last, in case the center is on translation as a portion of an real communication prepare, the foremost appropriate assignment for the related hypotheses is sociolinguistic. In genuine hone, of course, there's a significant degree of cover both within the detailing of standards and within the comparing proposals on strategies.

Conclusion. In conclusion wrong or inappropriate choice of words in the context of politically sensitive issues can lead to serious misunderstandings. DA attempts to determine why a particular word, phrase, or structure in the translation process was chosen over another. International politics to a large extent involves translation. Country-to-country agreements are available in multiple languages; Interpreters participate in the most important political events that facilitate the activities of international organizations such as the European Union, the United Nations, the League of Nations, etc. Some governments publish translations of important documents on their websites. As Schaffner points out, the media play an important role in disseminating politics and ideology.

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